

**IMPROVING THE DESIGN OF LANDSCAPED LAND FOR IRRIGATION OF
DRYLANDS WITH THE HELP OF NATURAL RAINFALL. (IN THE CASE OF
NAVOI REGION).****Norpo'latov Maxsudjon Maxmudovich**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118770>**Abstract**

A natural landscape is a region-specific combination of climate, topography, vegetation, and soil characteristics. The science that studies the laws of such a combination is landscape science. It is the science of the landscape shell of the earth and its natural elements (natural-territorial and natural-anthropogenic complexes). Along with the concept of "landscape shell", the concepts of natural-territorial complex (THM) and landscape have taken the main place in classical landscape science. THM is defined as a collection of interrelated natural components (myogenic bases, air climate, water, soil, flora and fauna) in the form of regional compounds at different levels. To date, the concept of "landscape" is interpreted differently. The main thing is to understand the harmony of the landscape with nature, unity, as well as the landscape as a structural element of the landscape shell of the earth, including various rules.

Key words: landscape, relief, layer, anthropogenic, drop, rain, plant, myogen, shell, water, soil, lithogen, biota.

Rainfall irrigation is a short-term but frequent irrigation method that provides irrigation conditions close to natural rainfall. Principle of operation: water is delivered through a system of pipes with the help of a pump, and with the help of sprinklers, the flow is divided into drops and sprayed into the air. When watering plants, small drops are deposited without creating a cloud, without compacting the earth, and without gradually being absorbed into the soil. The operating parameters of the rainwater irrigation system must be suitable to ensure a uniform flow of water throughout the irrigation area. sprinkler irrigation is not recommended for irrigating lettuce, cotton, tomatoes, peas, and strawberries, as splashing water on leaves or fruits can damage them. .

Today, it is accepted to group them into three small systems: - geoma - inorganic natural components: lithogenic bases (the upper part of the earth's crust and the relief of the earth's surface), air mass around the earth, natural waters; - biota - flora and fauna; - soil-intermediate or biocomposite (organomineral) subsystem. Each component has its own characteristics. Usually, material, energetic, and informational are separated separately. The exchange of matter and energy between its components and parts is based on the interaction and connection of

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

the geospheres that make up the geographic crust and ensure its development. This exchange is in the form of circulation of matter (for example: circulation of water, circulation of chemical elements, biological circulation, etc.).

Landscape planning options in the field of agricultural land use are defined by state-level legislative acts. Such legislative acts include the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It defines land relations as land use and protection relations, ensuring equality of land use and protection concepts in all articles of the Land Code.

Picture 1

Irrigation was used as a means of manipulating water in alluvial plains by the Indus Valley Civilization, whose use is thought to have begun around 4500 BC and dramatically increased the size and prosperity of their agricultural

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

settlements.[6] The Indus Valley Civilization developed modern irrigation and water storage systems, including artificial reservoirs at Girnar dating to 3000 BC and an early canal irrigation system c. 2600 BC. Large-scale agriculture was practiced with an extensive network of canals used for irrigation. Farmers in Mesopotamia used simple irrigation from the third millennium BC.[8] They developed perennial irrigation, regularly watering crops during the growing season by coaxing water through a matrix of small channels formed in the field.

Picture 2

Ancient Irrigation Works Sri Lanka had one of the most complex irrigation systems in the ancient world, the earliest dating back to 300 BC during the reign of King Pandukabhaya and continuous development over the next millennium. In addition to underground canals, the Sinhalese were the first to build entirely artificial reservoirs for water storage. Most of these irrigation systems are still intact in Anuradhapura and Polonnaruwa, thanks to advanced and precise engineering. The system has been extensively restored and expanded[by whom?] during the reign of King Parakrama Bahu (1153–1186 CE)

Sprinklers can also be installed on moving platforms connected to a water source with a hose. Self-propelled wheeled systems, certain sprinklers can irrigate unattended areas such as small farms, sports fields, gardens, pastures and cemeteries. Most of them use long polyethylene pipes wrapped around a steel drum. The sprayer is pulled across the field as the tubes are wound around a drum powered by irrigation water or a small gas engine. The system shuts off when the

sprinkler returns to the coil. This type of system is known to most people as a "water bucket" mobile irrigation sprinkler, and they are widely used for dust removal, irrigation, and discharge of waste water to the ground.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic country of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2016
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2017
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Ensuring the rule of law and human interests is a guarantee of the development of the country and the well-being of the people. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2017
4. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Action strategy on five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan. T., Uzbekistan, 2017 "Newspaper. en» Avezboev S.A., Volkov S.N. Landscaping design (textbook). Tashkent, "New century generation", 2004
5. Isayev S. X., Qodirov Z. Z., Oripov I. O., & Bobirova M. B. (2022). EFFECTS OF RESOURCE-EFFICIENT IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATION OF SUNFLOWERS ON LAND HYDROGEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS. British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development, 4, 95–100. Retrieved from <https://journalzone.org/index.php/bjgesd/article/view/55>
6. Egamberdiyev, M. S., Oripov, I. U., Hakimov, S., Akmalov, M. G., Gadoyev, A. U., & Asadov, H. B. (2022). Hydrolysis during hydration of anhydrous calcium sulfosilicate. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 4, 76-81.
7. Egamberdiev, M. S., Oripov, I. U., & Sh, T. S. (2022). Development of a Method for Measuring the Layered Moisture State of Concrete and Various Bases. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 4, 82-84.
8. Qodirov, Z. Z., Oripov, I. A., Tagiyev, A., Shomurodova, G., & Bobirova, M. (2022). WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN SOYBEAN IRRIGATION, EFFECT OF SOYBEAN ON GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 3, 79-84.